

SUB ROSA VOLUME I: BLOOM IN SECRET

by

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VOLUME I

Bloom In Secret

I

“Roses are red, violets are blue. Roses are red, violets are blue. Roses are_”

“Iris.”

I lift my head up to the sound of my name being called. Camelia is leaning against the door frame to my office. How long has she been standing there?

“Iris, are you listening?”

I had not been listening at all, I couldn't hear anything besides my own thoughts. I stood up slowly and concentrated on keeping eye contact with her.

“I'm sorry Camellia, could you repeat what you said please.”

She scoffs lightly, an unamused smirk befalling her lips. She steps slightly closer to me now, closing in on me. The smell of her expensive perfume wafts up into my nose, reminding me exactly where we are. She steps in front of me, slowly lifting her eyes from the floor to meet mine.

“The party. what are you wearing to it?”

“What party?” My uninterested tone comes off harsher than I expected.

She peels off of the door frame to step more into my workspace, taking a few more steps towards me.

“The reunion party. It’s this weekend; did you already forget?”

I did forget, in fact I have been trying my hardest to put that event at the back of my mind.

Pursing my lips in slight annoyance, I step out from behind my desktop.

As I move around my desk I step aside to her. “I’m not going,”

I say briskly making my way to the drawing board at the far left of my spacious office unit; I can hear the soft clicking of her heels chasing mine.

As I begin to softly rip paperwork off of the board, I can hear her let out an impatient sigh.

“and why not?”

“I don't have time to waste, my next project is a heavy one.”

She scoffs again, this time louder, shaking her head in disapproval.

“Always making your work your whole life.”

I turn around abruptly, “it IS my whole life camellia.” I state firmly.

She counters back in the most obnoxious way possible, “because you let it be.”

I turn my back to her once again to continue ripping off retired material when I hear her step beside me, staring directly at the side of my face. My silence only drives her past annoyance into frustration.

“Give me one reason why you’re not going.”

“I have work to do camellia. I don’t have time to-”

“You never took your 30 minutes.” looking across the room to the large digital clock hung on the wall. I let out a small puff of air.

As I turn my attention back to the drawing board I whisper faintly, “I don’t need a break.”

“Legal would think otherwise. Stop avoiding it.”

I let out a frustrated sigh. That single breath is so heavy I have to expel it from my body.

“I am not avoiding, I am working, something you should be doing, don’t you think?”, I spit with a bit of an attitude. As much as I would like to keep my patience, this conversation is draining me faster than my daily cup of coffee.

She gives me a tight smile, “You know I’m just here to support you right.”

“Is this how you plan on supporting me? Distracting me from my work and hounding me about my reasons for not going to some party.” I say crossing my arms trying to look as displeased as I feel.

“This isn't just some party, Iris. It's our high school reunion.”

“Exactly my point, how many people have you kept in touch with since high school?”

“Lots of people. You, Sunni, Nina, and_” she pauses mid sentence. I raise an unamused eyebrow at her silence. She swallows softly, “and Rose.”

Reflexes getting the best of me; my whole body tenses. She must have picked up on it by the way her gaze falls from my face slowly down, analyzing my posture.

I quickly turn around to avoid any more eye contact, and make my way back to my desk to pick up files for my next project. Something to relax my tense muscles and keep my mind in the present.

Camellia chooses to stay silent as I make my way back to the drawing board with a new stack of papers tucked in under my arm. I set them down softly on a small white coffee table, before picking up the first sheet and pinning it in the center. I continue to search through files when she steps closer.

“This is about Rose, isn't it?”

I angrily tear another sheet of paper off of the drawing board. “This is not about him. I didn't even know he would be going.”

“I disagree.”

I continue to aggressively post the new project detail sheets and informative stick notes to the drawing board, doing my best to drown any potential thoughts that could arise about

him. Camellia has always been forward, but she never knows when to stop. After so many years being the target of her nagging, I've learned it's best to just nod and make eye contact a few times a minute so she thinks I'm still listening to the words spilling out her mouth. I'm typically more patient with these conversations, willing to dissect my unwillingness to do or go somewhere she wants to drag me to, but just not today. When I'm here, in the office at work, I only want to think about this. I dedicate myself to being fully present, immersed in my work so they can be perfect for my clients.

I take a deep breath before reaching for the next page. I scoff; the irony of it. I look down at a printed picture of a blooming red rose. I peer down at the picture for a minute too long before picking it up. Reaching to grab a push pin from the small acrylic box placed on the coffee table, I can feel Camellia still staring at me in silence, waiting for my next words.

Grabbing a red pin from the box I slap the print out of the rose to the center of the board.

“Please just let me do my work in peace, Camellia, I need to focus.”

“You need to face him and get closure. Maybe it will help you-”

“I don't need any help.”

I let out a deep sigh, suddenly feeling a warm liquid trickle down my index finger.

“Iris.. your finger.”

“What about my-” I look back to see the small cut the push pin has made at the top of my index finger. Too trapped in the conversation, my lack of focus on the physical task at hand made me undershoot my pin target. I retract my hands from the board, applying pressure to

my injured finger. Red blood makes its way down my finger to graze my knuckle. Keeping my gaze on my injury, I walk slowly to stand in front of the glass door to my office.

“Please go back to work, Camellia.”

I softly push the door open with my foot just enough for me to squeeze through. As I walk away from her I can feel the stinging in my finger grow and my anxiety begin to heighten.

II

I have been anxious all of my life. Even when I was a child, back before I knew what anxiety was and how horrible it felt. Always being too cautious, always playing it safe, and always second guessing myself in everything I did. I have always lived like this, but it was never this hard to mask it before. My ability to completely disguise my illness was remarkable; even I bought my own con after a couple years of forcing myself to socialize and smile at everyone who passed by me. I could have gone my whole life pretending to be the most happy and fulfilled person in the room because my strength to hide my true feelings from those around me was stronger than my will to allow people to help me through it. I had been fooling everyone until I met Camellia.

It's like she could see right through me.

I remember the feeling of anxiety hitting me like a tidal wave on my first day of middle school, so much so that my hands shook slightly. I could feel someone slowly approach me from behind.

Feeling a gentle tap on my right shoulder, I slowly turned around to see a bright eyed girl. She smiled at me and extended her hands. I peered down at her hands while fidgeting with my shaky ones. I was confused at why she was extending her hands to me until she took my hands in hers.

Soft warm hands firmly held my mine, the vibration of my shaking made both sets of hands move.

“Breathe with me.” She says softly and I lift my head up to see her already staring back at me. She slowly takes a deep breath in and I follow suit, filling my little lungs with air. Letting the air out of our lungs she gives my hands a reassuring squeeze. The shaking of my hands has disappeared just like that and I'm left completely confused on how this girl knows how to calm me down or how she does it at all.

I guess she can see the confusion displayed on my face in the form of furrowed eyebrows and uncertain eyes. She smiles at me again and slowly lets go of my hands.

“My mom’s a psychiatrist and she helps people with their anxious tendencies.”

My head tilts to the side a bit. “Anxiety?” I question genuinely.

She nods firmly, “yes, your hands were shaking a lot. People with anxiety, well, sometimes their hands shake when they are feeling really anxious.”

I let my head fall a little in embarrassment, feeling ashamed of being found out.

“Oh, I’m sorry.” I apologize quietly.

“You don't have to apologize, you didn't do anything wrong.”

I lift my head up swiftly, eyes a little watery. She spoke words I had never heard before and it left a foreign feeling in my chest.

A knock at my office door brings me down from my thoughts, leaving me feeling strangely empty.

“Come in,” I call out softly.

Alina, my secretary, opens the door slowly just enough to fit the first half of her body through the door frame. Her short freshly styled hair falls softly to the side with her position. She smiles softly at me, “you should head home soon boss, the rain is picking up.”

I take a moment to turn my chair to look out of the window, eyes following the droplets of water cascade down the glass. When did it start raining in the first place?

“Get home safely!” she says quickly shutting the door before I could even get a word out.

With a deep sigh I stand up out of my seat. I had been so caught up in my work that I completely lost track of time and the weather. I glance at the clock above the door.

7:27 pm

I sigh softly, beginning to pack up my things. Shutting down my work computer, I make sure to print out any lasting details for my next project. After having secured everything, I quickly leave the office, bidding goodbye to the remaining staff still working away in their cubicles.

It takes me all of 20 minutes to get down to the parking garage with the constant stopping of the elevator and making small talk with other colleagues leaving work later than usual.

Driving home gives me time to think about what Camellia had been inferring, letting the pointed accusations trickle down into the puddle of thoughts inside my mind.

Did I really not want to go because there was a possibility Rose would be there?

Not that it was a possibility; more like a definite yes he was going to be there. He was always the party going type, so the chance I would have run into him at the reunion would be more than likely.

But then again, he was a detective now. Surely he'd have other pressing matters to attend to than go to some high school reunion. At least I hope he did.

Thoughts continued to cloud my mind, reflecting the busy sky on this stormy night.

I just hope by the time I find myself at my doorstep, all thoughts of this will leave me, allowing me to enjoy my nightly routine and the slumber that follows.

Walking through the rain is peaceful, the heavy droplets seem to cleanse the air of its toxins, leaving me clean from my daily dose of pollution. The revolving door into the apartment lobby is illuminated by small underground lights of a pale warm white.

A light push leads me through the swiftly shifting doors and into a warmer environment. The lobby smells like vanilla and honeysuckle, a sickeningly sweet smell that is all too familiar, but never loses its welcoming feel.

“Lady Iris, welcome home.”

I let out a small relieved sigh, “Monty, how has your evening been?”

“Wonderful my lady, how was your workday?” He slowly makes his way around the reception desk to greet me fully.

“Busy as usual, but I have a new project I am thrilled to work on.” I smile at him softly as he takes my hands in his large slightly wrinkled hands.

“How wonderful. It warms my heart to see my favorite tenant so happy.” His eyes twinkle with a warm fondness. A smile stretches across my face at the compliment, feeling relieved that my presence here has been a favorable one.

“Thank you Monty, truly,” I respond airily, eyes becoming slightly watery. He continues to smile at me, but slowly releases my hands from his grasp.

“Before I let you go, there was a delivery for you today.”

My eyebrow lifts in curiosity, slightly confused.

“A delivery for me?” I stand there perplexed.

“Yes,” he swiftly makes his way back around the desk, bending down out of sight to retrieve a package from one of the cabinets. “A young man dropped it off about 15 minutes before your arrival.”

He comes back around to me with a medium sized box in hand. I slowly take it from him, examining the tag placed neatly on the white bow wrapped tightly around its width. The box is indeed addressed to me, with no sender name, and no visible note other than my name.

“Thank you Monty, I’ll be heading up now.” I look up at him swiftly, bidding him a small goodnight on my way to the elevator. He calls out a hearty goodnight to me as the doors to the elevator ding open.

As soon as the doors close, I stare down at the box. Lifting it up to my right ear, I softly shake it to clear some of the mystery of what may be inside. There is a soft rattling, too faint to be anything heavier than paper. A soft ding signals the arrival of the elevator to my floor, the doors swiftly open.

The hallway is so quiet, the clacking of my heels disturb the peace arrogantly. I swiftly make my way around the corner, continuing to my apartment at a hurried pace. The curiosity of the contents in this package, joined with a slight impatience I have for the long walk to my home propell my legs to move a little faster than usual after a long day at work.

Reaching the front of my residence, I slowly pace my card holder against the frame. A blue light flashes prompting me to key in my apartment code. My fingers move swiftly over the touchpad, green light fills my vision and the door clicks unlocked. Pushing my way through the door frame, I quickly close the door behind me and place the door lock on it. Once inside my space, I walk straight to my small office, turning the low light on as I enter. I cannot bring myself to do anything else until I know what is in this box, slowly placing the box down on my desk.

I shrug my coat off of my shoulders, letting it fall slowly and then placing it on my desk chair. I pull the chair out lazily and drop down into the seat. Reaching across my desk, I once again pick up the box. Pushing the wrapping off the body of the box, I place it down again to wiggle the top off. Once the lid is up, I gaze down into the box.

My eyebrows furrowed, I slowly reach down into the box to pick up two stems.

Lifting the flowers up to get a better look, I am met with familiar sights of a Blue Salvia and small White Clover. Wrapped around the two thin stems is a dainty white ribbon tied in a small bow, joining the two. Looking back into the bow, I find the source of the faint rattling I heard in the elevator. My suspicion is correct, a small white envelope sits at the bottom.

I slowly place the flowers down on my desktop, pulling on the envelope with my opposite hand.

Opening it, I am met with a small white note with a pencil sketch of an iris, surrounded by thorns. At the bottom of the note, a message.

“The flowers speak,” I read aloud, slowly looking back over at the gift resting on my right.

One Blue Salvia and One White Clover. Staring at them gives me a minute to allow my brain to process before the sentence leaves my lips in a hushed tone.

“Think of me, as I think of you.”

III

“Think of me, as I think of you.” keeps ringing between my ears all night long, making it difficult to sleep. Someone is out there right now thinking of me and expecting me to think of them. The thought itself kept my mind racing in circles.

I have absolutely no clue who wants me to think about them, or why they are thinking of me in the first place. I can't think of a single person whose life I have impacted so much to the point where they are thinking about me on a normal Friday night. They even sent me a gift and I have no way of knowing why or how they know my address. It is frightening.

There is only one person that I can think of that would have access to information like my name and address, and I hope to god I was just overthinking this. Surely he has better things to do than to mess with me. Actually, this would be the perfect time to mess with me, a few days before the reunion, enough time to stir my thoughts and unsettle my stomach. I let out a long forced exhale, my chest sinking. I slowly shift onto my side, looking out the window of my apartment. The sky is a cool gray, still upset from the storm last night. My slight reflection in the window pauses my thoughts. I stare back at myself in the window. You can almost see the paranoia clouding my features. The dark circles under my eyes are beginning to concern me. I don't think one coat of concealer will do this morning. Concealing the evidence of my exhaustion as one motivation to get up, I slowly rise from the comfort of my bed, slowly shifting off.

The soft pattering of my footsteps fill the room, along with the sound of a soft flick as I switch on the lights to my bathroom. I let myself be consumed by my usual morning routine, clearing my head for just a moment. Looking up from my sink after brushing my teeth, I can take my appearance in one more time before leaving to select the outfit of the day.

Clearly I needed something that would cheer me up. I need something that will give me the strength to get through the day and make me strong enough to decide whether or not I would face him on Saturday.

I walk slowly parallel to my clothing rack, preselected combinations hung neatly on hangers. I am an organized person at my very core, every move calculated and it has made my life much simpler. My fingertips graze over the different textures, stopping on a luxurious obsidian tweed. The corners of my lips curl upwards. I absolutely adore this set.

An obsidian tweed blazer, paired with high waisted dark gray slacks, a vanilla white button up. Simple yet elegant. I take a few moments to get dressed, leaving the top button up open, just enough to be able to see the gold necklace adorning my neck. I take a few more moments to accessorize: gold jewelry and my favorite work stilettos. Spinning on the ball of my foot, I face towards the full length mirror. This is definitely the boost in confidence I needed. There is something about a nice outfit and a good makeup day that lifts my mood. I can just feel the difference in my steps already. A soft ringing calls my attention from across the room, walking out of the closet I catch a glimpse of my phone on the nightstand. I wonder who could be calling me this early in the morning.

Camellia <3

Flashes across my screen and I let out a small sigh.

Softly tapping the green accept button, I lift the phone up to my ear.

“Good morning.”

“Good morning Iris-” there is a pause in her voice, “have you left for the office yet?”

“No, but I’m just about finished and ready to go. Why?” My voice came out a bit stoic, more than I expect it to be even for the morning.

“Well I was wondering if we could carpool today, I want to talk to you before we head into the office.”

I feel a lump form in my throat, a defensive thought already seeping into my mind.

“Sure, what’s your ETA?” I begin gathering my things as I wait for a response.

“I’m downstairs in the lobby actually,” she exhaled softly.

“I’ll be right down,” I sound curtly, hanging up swiftly, leaving no opportunity for a response.

Swiftly stepping out of my apartment and securely locking the door behind me, I hurry down the hallway to the elevator. Once in the elevator, I begin to fidget with my attire, shifting my weight from foot to foot. As the elevator slows to a resting stop, I fidget for the last time just before the doors open, revealing Camellia.

She is as beautiful as ever. Long blonde hair curled in gentle waves, slender figure adorned with a matching cream tweed blazer and skirt set. Her ivory skin glowing under the bright lights of the lobby. She has always been beautiful, an asset most useful to her in many different ways.

I slowly approach her, a smile slowly making its way onto my face. She stretches her arms out to me, opening up a space for me in her arms.

Stepping closer I sink into her embrace, feeling my muscles relax as she wraps her arms around me. I can smell her signature perfume, sweet and delicate, almost intoxicating. I remember helping her pick it out in the store. I remember telling her it was perfect. And it was perfect, it perfectly matched her in every way. After a long pause, we pull back to look at each other, arms still wrapped loosely around waists.

“Good morning Iris,” she smiles.

“Good morning Cam.” Using that nickname now would give the impression that I didn’t have any ill feelings towards her about yesterday. I am hoping she will pick up on that.

“Ready to go?”

“Yes, give me one second,” I turned around to face Monty behind his desk. “Have a great day Monty.”

He smiles at me and wishes me a good day in return. Turning back to camellia we silently make our way to her car. The drive isn't long. It could be because we use that time to talk informally, about how life is outside of work. The reunion isn't brought up again, for good reason I assume. I can tell both of us want to keep the peace and sacrifice any discussion for the sake of that peace. I can feel it though, the hesitation in her voice, like she is forcing herself to talk about anything but that dreadful event. We reach the office soon enough, and we are off to start another day.

We make our way through the building and up to our offices, greeting employees in their cubicles as we pass by. I finally reach my office, where my assistant is waiting for me with a bright smile and a cup of coffee. The work day goes as it typically does, me consuming myself in my projects and not taking a break when I should. I ring Alina to pick me up some Italian from the kitchen downstairs, and I work up until she knocks on my door about 15 minutes later.

Lunch is fast and I honestly can't wait to continue working on this project, no matter how annoyed I am at constantly seeing and smelling roses. Flower after flower, all day long, this was my life. Surprisingly, I never get tired of the soft silence and the solitude my job often brings me. It gives me enough time to think and sometimes enough time to distract myself from thinking. Today is the latter kind of day, except I am brought back into reality when my phone buzzes, slightly vibrating the glass beneath it.

I walk over to my coffee table cautiously, as if I am waiting for something to pop out of my phone screen and spook me. Picking it up slowly, the screen flashes awake.

A singular text notification: From Lily.

IV

Ring ring ring

The ringing of the school bell brought me out of my thoughts, suddenly there were arms wrapped around my waist startling me.

“Hello beautiful,” a warm breath fanned my neck, “how is my beautiful girlfriend today?”
A small smile spread across my face. It was Rose. I turned in his arms to face him, bring my arms up to wrap around his neck. He smiled brightly at me, rendering me a bit speechless. He prompted me to speak by raising an eyebrow, eyes scanning my face.

“Hello my love,” I whispered delicately, “I am doing well, now that you’re here.”

“Get a room you two.” I turned my head to the semi harsh voice to my right.

Two dark eyes stared into my soul, captivating my attention.

“Lily, hey.” I slowly pull away from my boyfriend, stepping closer to her.

She stood there arms crossed, seemingly upset. Her perfectly tailored school uniform, with small accessories adorning her figure, caught my attention briefly. My eyes scanned back up to her eyes and I responded to her angry gaze with a half smile.

“Can you keep your pda to a minimum, some of us actually come here to study.”

“Is that so,” I gave her a challenging look before stepping closer to her, “well I've come to study too.”

She raised a skeptical eyebrow at me, “study what, anatomy?”

“No, psychology, actually,” I lunged at her wrapping my arms around her neck in a tight hug.

“Studying the effects hugs have on human emotion,” I laugh while swaying her softly side to side.

She didn't make any effort to block my advancement, or shrug me off, she only wrapped her arms around my waist, squeezing me closer. I could feel her place her chin on my shoulder. We stayed like that, swaying softly for a little as I laughed at her. She was always grumpy until I gave her a hug. She wasn't really a morning person.

I pulled back from her to scan her face, she was smiling brightly.

“Come on, let's go to class,” I rushed and grabbed her hand as the bell began ringing again.

Peering down at my phone, I couldn't believe my eyes. Lily had texted me. I couldn't remember the last time I talked to her, after everything that happened between us and the whole ordeal with Rose, I was convinced our friendship was more than over.

The text read:

“Violet, I know the reunion is coming up soon but I'd like to meet with you before then. There are some things I need to talk to you about. Are you free for dinner tomorrow at 7pm?”

I let out a deep sigh, feeling the heaviness set on my chest. How should I respond? A part of me wanted that closure from her, but after a decade was it really relevant anymore? Has guilt been chipping away at her since highschool?

Needless to say I was conflicted, stuck between wanting to respond and wanting to throw my phone out of the window, so I had an excuse not to respond. All of those hurt feelings rushed back to me all at once. I placed my phone back down on the table, and turned my back to it. I didn't want to respond, or even think about it. Going back to my work drowned my thoughts out, helping ease my tension. The day went by quicker than I expected, and before I knew it it was well past my time to leave the office.

I packed away my things, and said goodbye to my staff before heading out of the office. I didn't spare my phone a single glance, wanting to keep the little peace I had right now. Driving mindlessly home, turning down familiar streets, finally reaching my home. I was exhausted, at least I felt exhausted. I trudged my way through the rotating door, almost colliding with the door on my way into the lobby. Monty came rushing around his desk to greet me, holding another small black box.

Another message I presumed, and my anxiety started rising in my throat.

We briefly greeted each other and he placed the small box in my hands. Saying my goodbyes, I hurriedly made my way to my apartment, eager to see what this box had in store for me.

Almost slamming my apartment door shut, I briskly walked into my office. Repeating the same motion as last time, I opened the box, swiftly revealing three white Astilbes, tied together by a thin white bow.

A shaky breath leaves my lips before these next words do.

"I'll be waiting for you."

VI

As the night wore on, I found myself consumed by the unsettling reality of the messages. The notion of an admirer was quickly dispelled, replaced by the chilling truth-I had a stalker. A stranger, privy to the most intimate details of my life-my name, workplace, schedule, even my room number.

They also know that I speak the language of flowers, or at least understand it enough to decode the messages they send me.

It all circles back to the same question I had after opening the first box, why me?

Me, Violet Iris Kre, why Iris Kre?

"Why me?" I whisper under my breath, lying on my bed, feeling a chill run up my spine.

I needed to put this at the back of my mind; the more time I dedicated to solving this riddle, the more I would begin to question my own state of being. I needed another problem to trouble me enough to take my mind off this.

I started wrapping my brain around the following problem when one flashed right to the front.

Lily's message.

I still had yet to reply to it. In truth, I don't know what to say. I was still stuck between resentment and forgiveness. I know it's horrible to harbor ill feelings towards people, but anyone standing in my shoes that night and to this day would not forgive her.

But it was Lily.

Lily, who had always made my world bigger.

Lily, who had always placed that crown on my head at my lowest points.

Lily, who had always protected me when my back was turned.

And it was Lilly who took advantage of my back being turned.

Lily, who had plunged that knife so far through my back that it stuck out of my chest in the front.

I reached over to grab my phone on my nightstand. The message bubble popped up again, reminding me that a decision had to be made on my end.

Without another thought, I slid open the notification, which took me straight to the conversation.

How do I start this..

“Hey lily_”

No. We are not close enough anymore for informal chat.

I had to remind myself that she was no longer Lily to me but Velillian Barone.

A stone-cold heiress with a killer fashion sense and an even more malicious personality.

“Velillian, it would be my pleasure to meet with you for dinner tonight at 7.”

My attempt at coming off cold hurt my pride; this isn't me.

I sent the text without a second thought.

A few minutes later, my phone buzzed again, an incoming message.

From Lily.

“Wonderful, here are the directions to the restaurant. see you at 7.”

I sigh deeply, my chest completely rising and falling.

I changed her contact name to what it should've been since the moment I met her.

Velillian Barone.

Nothing more, nothing at all.

VII

As I sat at my desk, staring blankly at the computer screen, I couldn't help but feel a sense of restlessness consuming me. The words on the page blurred together, becoming a jumbled mess of letters that made no sense to me. I tried to focus, to push the distractions aside and focus on the task at hand, but my mind kept wandering to other things.

My dinner with Velillian tonight especially distracted me. I found myself struggling to keep my mind on my work. Every time I tried to concentrate, my thoughts would inevitably drift back to her. Was I setting myself up by meeting with her?

I tried to reason with myself, to push aside the doubts and focus on the potential benefits of saying yes. Maybe this was my chance to confront her, to demand answers to all of the questions that had been eating away at me for years. Maybe this was my chance to finally put this whole mess to rest and be done with it. There was also the possibility that she wouldn't even bring it up, leading me to believe I was being anxious for no reason.

What if she was just trying to lure me in, to use me again? I had always known that Velillian was capable of anything, and the thought of being so gullible left a lump in my throat. I had to be brave, had to face her, I can't keep letting the past plague me.

Deep down I knew that I missed her.

The day continued as I put those thoughts to the back of my mind. Before I knew it, it was time to clock out. I had to go home and get mentally and physically prepared for this dinner.

Once I got home, I started to prepare. I stood in front of my closet, surveying the options available to me for the dinner with Velillian. I knew I needed something that would make a statement, something that would convey confidence and power. After a few moments of deliberation, I settled on a sleek black dress, something that would parallel her personal color palette and my own. That was always the thing we shared in common, fashion sense and the overwhelming love for the color black.

As I adjusted the hemline, I couldn't help but feel a sense of satisfaction at how sharp I looked. But I knew that the dress alone wouldn't be enough to make the impression I was aiming for. I reached for my jewelry box, selecting a set of gold accessories to complement the black dress. A dainty gold necklace with matching earrings and bracelet added the perfect touch of glamor to my outfit.

I spent the next few minutes doing my makeup, opting for a bold red lip to complete the look. My hair was already styled in loose waves, framing my face perfectly. I took one last look in the mirror, feeling confident and powerful.

I left my apartment in a rush. I hated being late, especially since being early always gave me the upper hand in these situations. My drive there was consumed with giving myself an encouraging pep talk, and creating a mental checklist of all the things I would confront her about.

By the time I entered the restaurant, my nerves seemed to subside. The maître d' greeted me with a friendly smile, leading me to a table draped in crisp white linen. As I took my seat, I couldn't help but admire the stunning views of the city skyline visible through the floor-to-ceiling windows. It was clear that no expense had been spared to create an atmosphere of opulence and exclusivity.

A few minutes had passed, and as I waited I went through my mental checklist again, but all of it seemed to disappear when she walked in.

Slender build, with long limbs and graceful movements that exude confidence and poise. Her complexion was fair, with a smooth and flawless complexion that glows with health and vitality, and features her makeup enhanced. High cheekbones, a slender nose, and full lips that curve into a stunning smile. She was smiling at me.

I stood up to greet her as she made her way between tables to reach me.

A rich shade of platinum flowed from her head down to her waist, sleek, straight locks that frame her face perfectly.

This was a new Velillian, but somehow she felt like Lily.

We exchanged curt hellos, and sat down. It felt like something was looming over me.

She smiled at me again, then said something that made my heart race in anticipation.

“I’ve been waiting for this for a very long time.”

VII

a mysterious point of view

She is absolutely intoxicating. Everything about her consumes you the moment you get to know her a little too well. Her scent is so strong, so alluring. I fell in love the moment I first laid my eyes on her. That short tennis skirt, polo, perfectly curled hair, and smile. That smile that melts me, manipulates me, and commands me. I've been waiting for her, praying for that day she will walk through my front door again. I wait to run my fingers through her hair. Feel her close and hold her tight.

And never ever let go.

IX

I never wanted to come to this reunion, but my intuition was telling me that there was a reason I had to be there tonight.

I wanted to stay home, to not show my face to people I hadn't seen in 10 years. As I walked into the high school reunion, I was struck with a wave of anxiety. The large hall was filled with people I hadn't seen in years, and memories of those teenage years flooded my mind. Everyone seemed to be having a great time, chatting and laughing, but I felt out of place all on my own.

As I scanned the room, I realized how much everyone had changed. Some people looked almost unrecognizable, while others seemed to have barely aged at all. I tried to remember names as people came up to me, but my mind drew a blank. It was like being in a sea of unfamiliar faces, and I couldn't shake the feeling of being lost.

I was just a spectator, watching from the sidelines. Until a familiar face popped out of the crowd and made their way over to me.

“You came!” Camellia yelled in excitement, crushing me in a hug. I could smell liquor and something sweet on her breath. Glad to see she was having such a wonderful time.

“I changed my mind,” I murmured under my breath.

“Well, I'm glad because there are so many people here who wanna see you.”

I cringed a little bit. I used the last of my social battery to get here and now I'm low on power for conversation.

Trying to push myself to mingle more, and catch up with old friends, the anxiety was just too overwhelming. I felt like an imposter, like the Iris these people knew was nowhere to be found. I could see it on their faces, the disappointment. Truth be told I wasn't the same Iris from highschool, I had moved on from that persona and matured.

Camellia was around and about talking with everyone and I barely managed to pull away from every conversation I got caught up in.

Eventually, I decided to call it a night. I said my goodbyes and walked out of the hall, feeling relieved to be away from the crowd. As I stepped out into the cool night air, I took a deep breath and let out a sigh of relief. The reunion may have been a challenge, but at least it was over..

“Iris.” A smooth deep voice rang through the crowd. I felt a chill run up my spine.

The one person I had hoped and prayed I wouldn't run into tonight.

It was too late for me to turn my back and pretend I didn't hear him call my name, he was already walking over to me.

This night couldn't get any worse.

“Rose.”

X

“So, did you show up of your own volition or did Camellia drag you along?” he questioned, faking a concerned tone.

I crossed my arms, holding my position as he stalked closer, his footsteps echoing in the space.

“On my own. It was nice to see you, though,” the lie slipped out of my mouth smoothly. I turned on my heel, giving rose my back as I began to walk away.

“You're running away. You haven't changed at all.”

The words halted me in my tracks. I turned around slowly to face him, anger evident in my eyes. I straightened my posture and gave him a slow glance from head to toe. I slowly slid my eyes up his figure until I reached his burning gaze.

“You wouldn't know whether I've changed or not, Kieran. And from the looks of it, you are still the same arrogant, intolerable little boy.” I stepped closer, heels clacking on the hard floor. “I can see the excitement in your eyes.”

I was almost toe-to-toe with him. “Being here reminds you of your peak; these girls stroke that fragile little ego of yours.”

“Tell me,” I hold my gaze as I step closer, chest touching the front of his leather jacket. “does it feel good, having all this attention?” the venom dripping from each word. I could hardly recognize my own voice.

He released an angry puff of air, turning his head away from me for a moment before leaning down the next. I could feel his breath fan my face. I kept firm in my stance, not backing away from the sudden proximity. He leaned in closer, lips brushing the shell of my ear.

“I do love all the attention you're giving me right now, Violet,” his voice husky upon breathing my name.

Placing my hands on his chest, I firmly push him away from me.

“You are so insufferable,” I remark, frustrated by his lack of reaction.

“Go get attention somewhere else; I'm leaving.” I turned again and walked down the hall, heading for the doors.

“I think you should stay. We have so much to catch up on.” His long strides catch up to mine.

“I have nothing to say to you,” I pull open the door, and he uses his left hand to close it before I can walk through it. His large frame blocked my exit.

“I beg to differ,” he smirked down at me.

“Move.”

He leaned against the frame of the door, “no.”

“I said move.” loud sirens interrupts me, making me jump in surprise.

The fire alarm was blasting at a high-pitched frequency, and a slight pain started in my ears. I feel a large hand clamp around my wrist, pulling me into a firm chest.

“Kieran-”

“Let's get out of the building.” he states firmly, beginning to pull me out through the door and down the stairs into the parking lot.

There was a crowd of people from the reunion already standing outside. Kieran tugged me along, walking us closer to the crowd. Once close enough, I tug my wrist from his grasp and, without a second thought, begin to walk through the panicked crowd.

I slowly try to push through the crowd, but the bodies are so tightly packed. The lights in the parking lot begin to flicker, and after a few seconds, completely shut off, leaving us all in complete darkness.

Frightened screams and a few gasps, everyone began to start shifting frantically.

The pressure from the crowd began to take effect on my lungs. I start to push through the crowd, gasping for air.

Suddenly, I feel an arm wrap around my waist, and a hand covers my mouth. My eyes widen at the sudden contact, and I begin to struggle. I could feel my body being dragged along, and the terror set in.

I'm screaming, but with all the commotion in the crowd, no one seems to hear me.

Something cold pressed into the skin on my neck, and I froze at the sudden contact. Warm, wet liquid trickled down my neck, and I could feel a hand slip into the front pocket of my slacks. I squeeze my eyes shut, a tear leaking from the corner of my eyes.

Suddenly, the pressure is removed from me entirely, and I gasp for air. I placed my hand instinctively over my neck. My panic delayed itself, disrupted by the sound of a scuffle in front of me.

The lights flicker back on, and my vision blurs due to the sudden brightness. When my eyes finally adjust, I see Kieran standing before me, ripped shirt revealing his torn torso, bleeding from a cut. His hair is messy, and blood is running from the corner of his mouth.

My emotions pour over me all at once, and I begin sobbing. He slightly stumbles over to me, and I lose my leg strength. Kieran wraps his arms around me as I fall, not allowing me to hit the ground with any impact.

His eyes scan me and settle on the hand, cupping my neck, zeroing in on the red liquid streaming down my neck.

“Violet, don't move your hand.” He's firm, and he begins to call for help. The crowd started to run towards us, and I could feel the anxiety of being surrounded building in my stomach.

“Someone call 911!”

I look around frantically, trying to catch a glimpse of Camellia.

“Iris! Iris!” a panicked voice rings out from the sea of people, getting louder and more frantic.

Camellia rushes through the crowd to get to me but is stopped by a male in our graduating class.

My vision begins to blur; voices becoming mingled and unclear. I take a glimpse of Camellia, her face twisted in fear, tears streaming down her cheeks. My gaze shifts to Kieran, still holding me with his hand cupping over my own, applying more pressure to my neck.

I could hear the ambulance sirens get closer, and for a split second, my vision became clear.

Staring through the open gaps between people's legs, lying on the gravel with a white bow tied around it, a small bouquet of begonias.

“I'm warning you..” I whisper under my breath, hardly audible.

“Violet,” Kieran calls out my name, but my head is spinning again.

I'm beginning to fade as the paramedics reach me, lifting me out of Kieran's arms.

My eyes begin to shut despite frantic calls from multiple voices telling me to stay awake.

My vision blurs again, and the sounds begin to fade to nothing. I could feel a reassuring squeeze on my hand; it was the last thing I felt before my world faded to black.